

PRACTICAL MECHANISMS AND ADVANTAGES OF CONTEXTUAL TEACHING IN MODERN EDUCATION.

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of theoretical and practical aspects of the application of the contextual teaching model in the modern educational system. The article highlights the main features and benefits of contextual education, including linking theoretical knowledge to practice, increasing student interest, introducing an individual-oriented educational approach, and enhancing professional training. The model has also been analyzed for its integration with modern pedagogical technologies, such as multimedia, simulations and online platforms, and for its importance in improving the effectiveness of teacher-student communication.

Keywords: contextual teaching, theoretical knowledge, practical skills, personality-oriented education, professional training, interdisciplinary integration, modern pedagogy.

Introduction. The modern educational system is of great importance in adapting to the socio-economic development of society and meeting modern requirements. The organization of educational processes in education in a more efficient and practice-oriented way is one of the main aspects of modern requirements. In this context, contextual teaching technologies are of great importance as an innovative direction of Education. These technologies make it possible to inextricably link theory and practice, to form the professional and life skills of students, as well as to develop skills for independent thinking and solving practical problems.

Literature analysis and methodology. In the traditional educational model, the student only passively accepts theoretical knowledge and restricts the possibility of applying that knowledge in practice. This approach reduces the effectiveness of long-term memorization and implementation of knowledge into practice. Contextual teaching technologies provide a real-life adapted form of the learning process, as opposed to traditional approaches to education. Through this approach, students acquire the skill of applying theoretical knowledge to real situations. As a result, the real-life significance of the

knowledge gained among students increases and their readiness for practice is ensured.

Thus, the application of contextual technologies not only increases the quality of education, but also has a positive effect on the personal and professional development of those who receive education. The importance of contextual teaching is manifested, on the one hand, in the possibilities of putting into practice innovative approaches to modern education, and on the other hand, in improving the quality of education and serving to form student professional competencies. This approach will help improve the didactic and methodological aspects of the educational process, creating an interesting and meaningful learning environment for students . This ensures that students not only consolidate their theoretical knowledge, but also develop their practical abilities in solving real-life problems. At the same time, identifying the problems that arise during the inclusion of contextual teaching in the educational process and offering them effective solutions will lay the groundwork for its more successful application in pedagogical activity.

In pedagogical theory, the contextual teaching model is formed on the basis of many years of research and practical experience. This model is formed from the synthesis of approaches such as personality-oriented approach, activity-based education, integrative pedagogy, and constructivism. The personality-oriented approach plays an important role in shaping the basic principles of the contextual model, as in this model, the educational process is adapted to the personal needs and interests of students. Activity-based education, on the other hand, provides for the orientation of the educational process to practice and the active participation of students.

Discussion and results. The role of the contextual model in the educational system is manifested primarily in the fact that it differs from the traditional approach based on memorization and recall of knowledge. In this model, the educational process is aimed at developing skills such as solving real problems, critical thinking and independent decision-making. At the same time, this model is important in ensuring the integration between education and production, serving to effectively organize the process of preparing students for the labor market.

The contextual teaching model offers a number of advantages in the modern educational process:

1. Linking theoretical knowledge with practice. Students receive the opportunity to apply the theoretical knowledge they are learning in real-life situations. This will help them better understand learning materials.
2. Increase interest and participation. The contextual approach increases the interest of students, making them an active participant in the educational process. This, in turn, increases the effectiveness of Education.
3. Develop problem solving skills. This model teaches students to think and make decisions independently in problem situations, which enhances their professional training.
4. Personality-oriented education. The contextual model allows education to be tailored to individual needs, which promotes each student to achieve their abilities and goals.
5. Strengthening professional training. Students strengthen their knowledge through practical experience, increasing their competitiveness in the labor market.

Due to these advantages, the contextual teaching model is manifested as an effective approach to the development of the educational system and ensuring the professional and personal development of students. At the same time, the successful application of this model is important in strengthening the inextricable link between education and production.

In the process of contextual training, modern didactic tools and technologies play a decisive role. Multimedia tools, such as audio-visual materials and interactive presentations, make it easier to understand complex topics. Simulation and virtual reality tools serve as effective tools in preparing students for real-world professional situations, as through these technologies students will be able to put their theoretical knowledge into practice in a safe and controlled environment. Online platforms, such as Moodle or Google Classroom, support independent student learning and engage them in project activities. At the same time, interactive games and problematic assignments will help to increase student activity, increase interest in the educational process.

Contextual teaching classes are formed from several main stages. At the preparatory stage of the lesson, educational goals are determined, and problem situations are selected. These situations will be designed to encourage students to think and increase their interest. At the activity stage, students complete tasks aimed at solving real problems. This process involves group work, role-playing games, or simulations, which encourage students to make independent decisions and think critically. At the analysis and discussion stage, students analyze their

activities and evaluate their results. This process helps to strengthen knowledge and compare different approaches. At the final stage, the topic of the lesson is summarized, students draw conclusions about how their theoretical knowledge can be applied in real-life situations.

The practical mechanisms of the contextual teaching model are important in coordinating the modern educational system with the needs of students and the real demands of society. These mechanisms organize the pedagogical process in such a way that students put theoretical knowledge into practice and prepare for their professional activities. Specific methods for effective application of contextual teaching, interdisciplinary integration and the organization of effective dialogue between the educator and the students are the main factors.

Conclusion. The role of the approach in improving the quality of higher education is also manifested in establishing an effective connection between students and teachers. The interactive and person-oriented organization of the learning process helps to develop a reliable dialogue between the teacher and the student. This, while making the educational process interesting and effective, serves to instill in the students a deep mastery of the teaching materials. This ensures the quality of education and continuity in the supply of ready-made personnel to the labor market.

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